

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II) Succinimide with Ammonia and Aliphatic Amines

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Succinimide forms a yellowish green coloured complex with cobalt(II) in presence of aliphatic amine. This colour formation was only due to the equilibrium between tetrahedral and octahedral complexes. The complexes could be isolated in the solid form, analysed chemically and their structures were established on the basis of magnetic and conductance measurements and I.R. and visible spectra.

THE simple and mixed ligand complexes of phthalimide with cobalt(II) using ammonia, dipyrindyl and *o*-phenanthroline as secondary ligands have been studied in relation to their preparation, magnetic and I.R. studies¹⁻⁴. Such types of studies with succinimide are reported only with copper(II)^{5,6}. Nothing has so far been done on the mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) succinimide using ammonia and aliphatic amines as secondary ligands.

Preliminary studies indicated the formation of highly soluble, yellowish green coloured cobalt succinimide complex in presence of ammonia or aliphatic amines in aqueous dioxane (8 per cent. dioxane, V/V or more) medium. The present communication deals with the structures of these mixed ligand complexes in solution as well as in solid state, on the basis of conductance, I.R., electronic spectra and magnetic measurements.

Materials and Methods :

Absorbance measurements at varying wave lengths were recorded with a Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20 using matched glass cells of 1 cm path length. Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on specord—VS. Magnetic measurements were made by Gouy's method. Conductivity measurements were made with a Phillips conductivity bridge using a dip type conductivity cell. pH measurements were made with Beckmann pH-meter model H using glass electrode. I.R. spectra in the region 4000-300 cm⁻¹ were run in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer-337 spectrophotometer.

All the reagents were of A.R. quality. Succinimide was recrystallised from ethanol. All the solutions were prepared in 10 per cent. (V/V) dioxane.

Results and Discussion

Nature of the Colour Reaction : Vosburgh and

Cooper's method⁷ applied to the ternary systems (mixtures of Co(II) succinimide and amines in different ratio) gave a maximum at 330 nm while that of cobalt itself absorbs strongly at 490 nm and cobalt amine complexes absorbs strongly at around 535 nm (Fig. 1.) This λ_{\max} of ternary species was independent of the amine chosen. So the wave length 330 nm has been used for these studies. At least four fold excess of succinimide and two-fold excess of amine is necessary for full colour development. The colour saturation curves are given in Fig. 2. The most suitable pH for full colour development lies between 9.5 to 10; 10 to 10.8; 10.4 to 11.0 and 10.5 to 11.2 in the case of ammonia, methylamine, ethylamine and isopropyl or isobutylamine respectively. The colour formation was instantaneous and remained stable for twenty-four hours, afterwards it became turbid.

Structure of the Complexes : A highly soluble yellowish green coloured product formed on mixing the solution of cobalt(II) succinimide and amine in 10 per cent. (V/V) dioxane in the ratio of 1 : 4 : 2 respectively was precipitated on heating to 60°. The dark-green coloured precipitates were filtered off, washed several times with the solvent and then dried in a vacuum desiccator. The chemical analysis for the metal and nitrogen (Table 1) and the molar conductance measurements in nitrobenzene corresponded to the formula [Co(succ)₂(Am)₂], where Am = ammonia or aliphatic amine. The magnetic moments were 4.7 ± 0.15, usually encountered for tetrahedrally coordinated cobalt(II). The electronic spectra of the complexes in chloroform gave two bands at \approx 515 nm and \approx 550 nm which is also a characteristic of tetrahedral structure.

The multicomponent nature of the visible band which in T_d symmetry corresponds to the transition ⁴A₂ - ⁴T₁(D) arises presumably from spin-orbit coupling and is frequently observed in the spectra of tetrahedral cobalt complexes. The variation of the position of the centre of gravity as the visible band

Fig. 1 Mixture containing :
 (1) Cobalt(II)-0.0025M, succinimide-0.01M and methylamine 0.005M.
 (2) Cobalt(II) only-0.025M.
 (3) Cobalt(II)-0.002M and methylamine-0.02M.
 (4) Cobalt(II)-0.005M and succinimide-0.02M.

Fig. 2 All solutions contained :
 Curve 1-0.002M, CoCl₂ and 0.008M, succinimide and varying conc. of methylamine.
 Curve 2-0.002M, CoCl₂ and 0.004M, methylamine and varying conc. of succinimide.

with change in amine leads to the following order of ligand field strength $NH_3 < CH_3NH_2 < C_2H_5NH_2 < C_3H_7NH_2 \approx C_4H_9NH_2$. This is the order of donor power of these molecules. Effect of varying ligand field strength seems to be reflected also in the magnetic moments of these complexes, e.g., the ammonia in which average ligand field is weakest has the highest moment 4.85 BM whereas the propyl and butyl amine having much greater ligand field have a moment of only about 4.55 BM.

These complexes were also examined spectrally in the visible range in both chloroform and nitromethane and also in nitromethane-containing about 10 per cent. of appropriate amine. The molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) for the spectra in solution without added amine are high (ϵ is 300 to 500) as expected for tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes. The addition of excess of amine in the solution of the complexes in nitromethane increased the height of

ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF THE COMPLEX IN NITROMETHANE

Fig. 3 Solutions in nitromethane :
 Curve 1-[Co(succ.)₂(methylamine)₃] complex 0.0020 M.
 Curve 2-[Co(succ.)₂(methylamine)₃] complex 0.00M containing 0.005 molar methylamine per litre.

tetrahedral absorption bands. Such an increase in the height of this band was not observed in chloroform.

The spectra of solutions containing (1) complex and a large excess of amine (2) cobalt(II) salt and a large excess of amine were quite different from each other which ruled out the possibility of the equili-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complexes	% Found		% Found		Magnetic Moment B. M.
	M	N	M	N	
[Co(C ₄ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂ (NH ₃) ₃]	20.29	19.15	20.40	19.38	4.85
[Co(C ₄ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂ (CH ₃ NH ₂) ₃]	18.45	17.46	18.58	17.67	4.75
[Co(C ₄ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂) ₃]	17.15	16.09	17.07	16.23	4.64
[Co(C ₄ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂ (C ₃ H ₇ NH ₂) ₃]	15.70	14.82	15.79	15.01	4.55
[Co(C ₄ H ₈ O ₂ N) ₂ (C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂) ₃]	14.78	13.80	14.69	13.96	4.50

TABLE 2—STRETCHING FREQUENCIES (cm)⁻¹ OF SUCCINIMIDE AND ITS METAL COMPLEXES IN I.R. SPECTRA AND THEIR ASSIGNMENTS

Succinimide	Metal Complexes [Co(succ) ₂ (Am) ₂]	Assignments
3200(b)	3200(S)	N-H
	849(S)	N-H out of plane deformation
1418(W)	1418(S)	C-N-C bending
1378(S)	1378(S)	C-N-C bending symmetric
1198(sh)	1198(S)	C-N-C bending (coupled)
1750(S)	1680(S)	C=O in PA and BA complexes
	1680(S)	C=O in EA complexes
	1650(S)	C=O in MA complex
	1645(S)	C=O in ammonia complex
1470(S)	1480(S)	C-N

S=Strong, W=Weak, sh=shoulder, b=broad, Am=ammonia or diphtic amines, MA=Methyl amine, EA=Ethylamine, PA=Propylamine, BA=Butylamine.

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Thus, it was quite evident that the yellowish green colour formed on mixing the reactants, i.e., cobalt(II), succinimide and amine, in 10 per cent. dioxane was only due to tetrahedral-octahedral equilibrium, i.e.,

The main characteristic bands of succinimide and its complexes are given in Table 2. Disuccinimido bis(aliphatic amine) complexes of cobalt(II) show N-H stretching vibrations around 3200 cm⁻¹. The carbonyl stretching frequency of the complexes fall within the range 1680-1645 cm⁻¹, which is well removed from the 1750 cm⁻¹ band observed in succinimide and 1700 cm⁻¹ band observed in cobalt(II) succinimide salt. The stretching frequency obtained at 1470 cm⁻¹ due to C-N in the spectrum of succinimide was shifted to 1480 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of its complexes. Although the C=O gp in succinimide does not take part in coordination, the

infra red band corresponding to -C=O stretching was shifted to lower frequency compared to the non-coordinated state. This behaviour is just comparable to metal phthalimide complexes⁹.

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